

MODERN ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE TECHNOLOGIES

Qo‘choqorov Ma‘murjon Abdug‘affor o‘g‘li

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Annotation

This article provides information about modern artificial intelligence technologies.

Today, most people think of robots as assistants who can talk like humans and perform all tasks instead of them. But this is a much broader concept. In fact, several programs available on mobile devices: google-translator, dictionaries, various games, etc. are also examples of artificial intelligence. Only their scope is smaller and they help only the sectors in a certain direction.

Artificial intelligence usually deals with the creation of computer systems with capabilities associated with the human mind: language understanding, teaching, discussion, problem solving, translation, and similar capabilities.

To date, the world's giant IT companies are providing artificial intelligence programs designed to perform various tasks.

Below we will give information about these artificial intelligence programs:

Character.AI is a beta product that uses neural language models to enable users to collaborate with a computer to write dialog with the illusion that they are

talking with another character. It can be used for imagination, brainstorming, and language learning.

Picture 1. Character.AI

LeiaPix Converter enables instant conversion of 2D images into beautiful 3D Lightfield images. Export to Leia Image Format, Side-By-Side 3D, Depth Map, or Lightfield Animation. Upload an image to upgrade to Lightfield.

Picture 2. LeiaPix

Codeium is a programming superpower that enables developers to quickly make changes to unfamiliar languages and codebases using natural language. It also helps minimize boilerplate coding, find and use APIs, and generate unit tests. It supports Python, CSS, JavaScript, Java, and Regex.

Picture 3. Codeium

BlueWillow AI is an image generating AI tool designed to help users create logos, graphics, photo-realistic scenes, and more. The user simply enters a prompt and the tool will generate a wide range of images to be used for any project. It leverages multiple different AI?Image generation models, picking the best model for the prompt provided. The tool is user-friendly and accessible to everyone regardless of their experience or expertise. Users can join the Discord to test prompts, generate images, meet others, and get support.

Picture 4. BlueWillow

Visus allows you to train a ChatGPT AI on your documents and knowledge base. Uncover valuable insights from your data quickly and effortlessly. Visus.ai understands your language and learns from your documents, delivering personalized results tailored to your specific needs.

Picture 5. Visus

ChatPDF is a tool that enables users to interact with their PDF documents as if it were a human. It works by analyzing the PDF file to create a semantic index, then presenting the relevant paragraphs to a text-generation AI. It can be used to

quickly extract information from large PDF files, such as manuals, essays, legal contracts, books, and research papers. The data is stored in a secure cloud storage and deleted after 7 days.

Picture 6. ChatPDF

Upload documents and then ask it questions. This tool provides an easy way to quickly summarize long papers, get instant answers to difficult questions, and write papers 10X faster. It enables users to quickly discover new insights, generate detailed insights, and simplify complex technical papers.

Picture 7. Humata

Verbatik is an AI-powered text-to-speech generator that offers a growing library of over 600+ natural-sounding voices in 142 languages and accents. It allows users to create high-quality audio versions of articles and other text-based content, with features such as a powerful sound studio, SSML features, and unlimited revisions.

Picture 8. Verbatik

Voice AI Voice Changer is a voice cloning and voice changing tool that allows users to clone and create personalized voices for streaming, gaming, meetings, and calls. It supports a variety of platforms, including Among Us, World of Warcraft, MineCraft, CS:GO, League of Legends, Discord, Skype, Google Meet, Zoom, and WhatsApp. Additionally, it offers a Voice Universe tab for free public voices, a Voice Changer feature, a Soundboard feature (coming soon), and an easy-to-use SDK.

Picture 9. Voice.ai

Capturelab is a free tool that helps gamers grow their channels and showcase their best gaming moments. It uses advanced AI technology to automatically process streaming sessions, identify and highlight the most exciting and memorable moments, and create video reels that can be edited, connected, and shared on social media platforms. It's easy to use - simply connect your Twitch account and let Capturelab do the rest. Additionally, gamers can sign up for Adlab.gg to join sponsorship campaigns and make money from their streams.

Picture 10. Capturelab

AI Registers is an online ai tools directory that lists the latest and most innovative AI tools available. This directory provides users with a comprehensive list of AI tools, categorized by type, to help them find the perfect tool for their needs. The directory also provides detailed descriptions of each tool, as well as links to additional resources and tutorials to help users get started. With Ai Tools Directory, users can quickly and easily find the right AI tool to help them automate their processes and enhance their business operations.

Picture 11. AI Registers

The artificial intelligence tool **To Teach** provides teachers with personalized materials and exercises tailored to the interests and needs of their students. It offers both free and paid plans which include printable and digital materials, ready-to-teach worksheets, and the ability to create exercises, lesson plans, and use gamification options. It uses artificial intelligence to create practice exercises and personalize educational content.

Picture 12. to teach

A tool that allows users to turn text into a song. It uses natural language processing to convert textual input into an audio composition. The tool allows the user to choose from a variety of music styles and instruments, as well as adjust parameters such as tempo, key, and dynamics. The resulting track can be exported as a high-quality audio file.

Picture 13. Text-To-Song

Translate.Video is a video translation tool that enables users to easily translate their videos into multiple languages. The tool offers automated captioning, subtitle translation, dubbing, AI voice-over, recording, and transcript generation in one easy-to-use app.

Picture 14. Translate.Video

EmailMagic is the AI assistant that helps you write emails 10x faster. Let it be Your Digital Twin. It Writes Emails Just Like You!

Picture 15. EmailMagic AI

Playground AI allows more and easier control of image generation AI. Use DALLE-2, Stable Diffusion 1.5 & 2.0 along with Playground's filters to get the exact aesthetic you want. A free account comes with 1000 picture generations per day and free commercial license.

Picture 16. Playground AI

InteriorAI is an AI image generator platform that allows users to upload an image of their (or someone else's) home, and generate a new look and layout based on one of 17 preselected styles. It is part of a growing ecosystem of AI image

generators, and could be used for interior design ideation or real estate virtual staging.

Picture 17. Interior AI

AI Image Upscaler is a website that offers AI-powered tools for upscaling and enhancing images. It claims to use advanced computer vision algorithms to increase the resolution of images up to 4x while maintaining the details and textures of the original image. The website also offers a mobile app for iOS and Android and is free for personal use. It offers bulk processing and storage options for commercial or professional use through a separate product called PixelBin.io. The website also offers a range of other AI-powered image tools, including background removal, watermark removal, image shrinking, and more.

Picture 18. AI Image Upscaler

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